

Analytical method development for directed enzyme evolution research

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Abstract

Analytical methods were developed for a directed enzyme evolution research programme, which pursued high performance enzymes to produce high quality L-ribose using large scale biocatalytic reaction. A high throughput HPLC method with evaporative light-scattering detection was developed to test ribose and ribitol in the enzymatic reaction, a β -cyclobond 2000 analytical column separated ribose and ribitol in 2.3 min, a C_{18} guard column was used as an on-line filter to clean up the enzyme sample matrix and a short gradient was applied to wash the column, the enzymatic reaction solution can be directly injected after quenching. Total run time of each sample was approx. 4 min which provided capability of screening 4 \times 96-well plates/day/instrument. Meanwhile, a capillary electrophoresis method was developed for the separation of ribose enantiomers, while 7-aminonaphthalene-1,3-disulfonic acid was used as derivatisation reagent and 25 mM tetraborate with 5 mM β -cyclodextrin was used as electrolyte. 0.35% of D-ribose in L-ribose can be detected which can be translated into 99.3% ee of L-ribose. Derivatisation reagent and sample matrix did not interfere with the measurement.

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Biography

Wan Jee Lee has completed his PhD from University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA. He now serves as an Associate

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